

COMPOSER ABDIREYIM SULTANOV'S LIFE AND WORK

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Annotaciya: Biz bul maqalamızda Ózbekstan hám Qaraqalpaqstan Respublikasına xızmet kórsetken kórkem óner gayratkeri, ataqlı kompozitor Ábdireyim Sultanovtıń ómiri hám dóretiwshiligine baylanıslı ayırım máselelerdi úyreniwge háreket ettik.

Аннотация: В данной статье мы попытались изучить некоторые вопросы, связанные с жизнью и творчеством известного композитора Абдирейма Султанова, артиста, служившего Республике Узбекистан и Каракалпакстану.

Annotation: In this article, we tried to study some issues related to the life and creativity of the famous composer Abdireyim Sultanov, an artist who served the Republic of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan.

Gilt sózler: *mádeniyat, kórkem óner, muzika, kompozitor, nama.*

Ключевые слова: *культура, искусство, музыка, композитор, мелодия.*

Keywords: *culture, art, music, composer, melody.*

A song has served as the spiritual wealth of the people regardless of any historical changes in the life of the people. Art, along with providing a pleasant life to the people, inspires them to live a good life through their tireless work, supports them from the spiritual side, and guides them according to their dreams. The genre of the music of Karakalpak folk songs is very diverse. In a song, the melody and the lyrics are equally important, and they serve the same purpose. Valuable (powerful) songs have appeared due to the fact that the lines of the poetic text have always complemented each other in the songs of each folk song. A melodic caesura appeared as a result of combining the phrases in the melody with the lines of words in the text. The singers recited the hymns in order to memorize them and to make them believe in the people, which means that if the song is sung with a melody, it will

not be forgotten. Karakalpak folk songs depict historical events, programs, attempts to a brighter future, warm feelings for the country, loyalty to love.

Abdireyim Sultanov, who understood these points of view and concepts well, grew his love for the art of music from his youth. Musicologists and artists provide a lot of information about his life and work experiences in their artistic works.²⁸

Abdireyim Sultanov is widely known as an artist who served the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan, a famous composer, conductor, teacher, a member of the Union of Composers of Uzbekistan, and a political figure. A. Sultanov was born on May 15, 1930 in Chimbay district. While studying at school, he participated in a group of artistic amateurs and learned to play dutar, mandalina, and violin. From 1943 to 1949, A. Sultanov worked as a violinist in the state philharmonic named after Berdakh. The young talent began to create his first songs during these years and was encouraged to study. He studied at the faculty of folk songs of the Tashkent State Conservatory in 1949-1955. During his studies, he created the "Qaraqalpaq syuitasi" for the Karakalpak melodic orchestra, many lyrical songs, variations for violin, piano instruments, plays, polonaises, preludes and many other artistic works together with his teacher Professor B. F. Glienko. After graduating from the conservatory, A. Sultanov wrote music together with F. Nazarov for the musical dramas "Baxit", "Rawshan", and A. Khalimov together with the musical dramas "Qirli soqpaqlar", "Jasliq syuitasi", and the symphonic poem "Bozataw". Along with the works mentioned above, he wrote a series of 32 songs for Ajiniyaz's words, including "Sawdigim", "Gozallar", "Barmeken", "Bir janan", "Jol bolsin", "Kuba qus". He organized the Karakalpak folk song orchestra in 1956. Professors A. J. Petrosyanc, F. Nazarov, M. Nasimov, I. Akbarov helped him in such a good work. Since 1958, he has completely transferred to the orchestra of folk songs and performs the orchestra's repertoire and the orchestra's propaganda service throughout the republic. A. Sultanov actively participated in

²⁸ Адамбаева Т. Қарақалпақ совет музыкасының тарихынан. Нөкис. «Қарақалпақстан» 1985. Б-100-117.// Қарақалпақ композиторлары.(ҚРХБМ) Нөкис-2010. Б-10-12. // Nadirova A. Qaraqalpaq muzika tarixi.Toshkent. «Sano-standart». 2018. B-254-256.

the republic's cultural public social events, decades, cultural days, art festivals, siezd and plenums of the composers' union, auditions and meetings.

A. Sultanov's heritage is widely known to many people, his 300 works of art have a significant place in the repertoires of professional and amateur groups, and are included in the programs of educational institutions. Most of his music was recorded and preserved on gramophone records and in the phonetics of the TV and radio company in the collections "Qaraqalpaq xalıq namaları", "Qaraqalpaq muzikalı dramalarınan úzindiler", "Sáwdigim", "Ayt sen Ájiniyazdıń qosıqlarınan".

A. Sultanov was awarded with the title of the laureate of the award named after Berdakh, an artist whose work has been broken in Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan, for his great services to the development of the music culture of the republic. He was awarded medals and certificates of honor.

A. Sultanov died on September 15, 1992. For almost 40 years until the end of his life, the composer devoted his talent and energy to the development of the musical culture of Karakalpakstan. The musical language of A. Sultanov's works was distinguished by its simplicity, clarity, comprehensibility, harmony with the Karakalpak national melodies, and the skillful use of new means of musical influence.

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